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BORDERING PATHS FOR THE TEACHING OF VISUAL ARTS IN A DECOLONIAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This is an exploratory study based on a brief, and still partial, literature review on non-colonial theories for teaching Visual Arts. In large part, it is the result of questions that arose during my doctoral research on image production in Amazonian cultures, and the implications of erasing this visual narrative in art history, and which now unfold in the teaching practices of Visual Arts for students. early years of elementary school. The main objective is to organize a theoretical framework of initial reference, based on concepts that guide a decolonial teaching practice for Art, given the permanence of themes, contents and activities centered on European or North American culture. More specifically, I hope to forge paths capable of shifting the emphasis given to Western art and its canons - taken as the only relevant source of references in the teaching of the Arts -, to other cultures placed in a peripheral situation, and that despite their historical erasure and marginalization, are fundamental sources of knowledge and aesthetic experimentation for the formation of individuals capable of relating artistic production with analysis, historical information and contextualization, so necessary for expanding their visual repertoire and favoring their understanding of the cultural diversity that insists and persists in consolidating itself. as a political practice in the contemporary world.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching of Visual Arts has been marked for some years by conceptual and methodological changes and has been a challenge that instigates and demands changes in perception in relation to its themes and practices, especially in current times, when there is a social, political urgency, ethics and morals regarding processes that decolonize the fields of knowledge in favor of the visibility of different types of knowledge that make up the social fabric. These transformations in teaching also reflect how the scientific discipline of Art History has undergone significant changes, whether from the point of view of its objects of study, or the theories and methods that guide its analyses. As the significant efforts of researchers to incorporate more complex and diverse narratives about global artistic exchanges grow, the inclusion of new objects to the canons of the area also increases and a consequent revision of theoretical-methodological assumptions for the treatment of unique artistic traditions located outside the hegemonic European or North American perspective. In the case of Brazil, these transformations of the discipline seek to correct the lapses left by the exclusion of a significant part of the visual culture of its own territory, since the construction of the field of art history here was carried out via European tradition.

Like the academy, the school is, historically, a space for maintaining the hegemony of knowledge committed to coloniality and both need to be decolonized, bringing to the center of discussions other cultures, their narratives and epistemologies, arts and aesthetics made invisible by force. of the colonial project in disqualifying the diverse as illegitimate, folkloric or naive.

It is true that the National Curricular Parameters established an equivalent weight for Art in terms of importance as a discipline, but this did not even remotely solve the problems of its teaching, since they do not recommend plurality, but are an instrument of homogenization of themes. Another aspect is the teachers' training itself, which still lacks incentives and deepening to minimally guarantee the organization of a teaching practice that is capable of favoring knowledge about Visual Arts that relates artistic production with analysis, historical information and contextualization

(BARBOSA, 2012; MOURA, 2019).

To broaden my understanding of coloniality in art teaching, I turn to authors who explain the insurgency of the term de(s)colonial in the Latin American context, as a sharpening of criticism of the previous terms used to discuss the signs of failure of modernity projects, that is, post - colonial or post - modern problems . I also rely on research carried out in the field of Art Education to situate myself in terms of practices for identifying the dynamics of coloniality in the formation and instrumentalization of this knowledge, so that I can then direct the processes of decolonial practice and thus, possibly transform the parameters of perception and predominantly European or North American readings of the world that are still in force in the construction of imagery repertoires of art.

Following the example of the development possibilities of a decolonial project for teaching the arts in the early years of Fundamental, I bring to this study a design of the actions that I have developed in the learning spaces available at the Vira Virou school and that, despite being an experimental project, still under construction, has favored practical exchanges that I consider important for transforming the repertoires of students, fellow teachers and class assistants, strengthening the notion that guides the principles of the school that, in his words, strives

to build a genuinely Brazilian pedagogical proposal. Thus, in addition to the world knowledge and references that traditionally make up the school curriculum, we seek to add to the content grid the knowledge of Amerindian and African origin of the peoples that constitute our Brazilian identity. Thus, we expanded the references in our curriculum, seeking a richer cultural literacy for our children (Available at <https://www.viravirou.com.br/nossos-diferenciais>).

In this sense, I recognize the privilege of developing this project in an environment that pronounces and welcomes diversity, generating an active and transforming learning community.

THE DECOLONIZATION OF ART HISTORY AS A CONVERSATION STARTER

From research in the field of Visual Arts, I observed the problems of the hegemony of Western thought over other worldviews, their artistic productions and cultural expressions. Interested in studying Amazonian artistic production during my PhD, I did not find theoretical support in the History of Art to build my object. Despite the fact that Amazonian art, in the last forty years, has surpassed the borders of its production sites, meeting the demand of a foreign market voraciously interested in traditional cultures, their knowledge, medicines and in their art, it does not appear in the specialized literature, the not when framed in the category of naïve, naïve art or something like that. To continue the research, I resorted to the Anthropology of Art, a field that is already advanced in discussions about other worlds, cultures and possible cosmovisions. Thus, when I started teaching Visual Arts for elementary school, I already had the conviction that one cannot know about one's own cultural identity, massively studying references alien to one's own culture. And in this regard, there is nothing new, since researchers such as Ana Mae Barbosa have been dealing with the problem since the 1980s, but the need to discuss pedagogical practices that actually transform the colonized scenario of Visual Arts teaching remains pressing and will certainly take more a few years to gain clearer and more permanent decolonial contours.

Being part of a school community that resonates with Brazilian arts and cultures is an opportunity for teaching practice guided by the approach to the relationship between artistic production, historical contexts and unique, distinct and diverse cultural territories in relation to the teaching model guided by colonial. That is, a teaching practice capable of building a knowledge of artistic making that is crossed by the multiplicity of cultures and their

different historical contexts, whose aesthetic references can be rich for learning experiences in the field of Visual Arts, especially in the context of Brazilian culture, but on the other hand, not restricted exclusively to him.

I begin by trying to understand the notion of cultural diversity. The term points to the relatively recent search for the imagination of ways of counter-hegemonic rearticulation of this diversity as the foundation of the struggles of different peoples and of alternative and emancipating regional integration projects, from other, local and community knowledge and experiences and not exclusively cut out in the Eurocentric conception. of being and being in the world. But, according to BARBOSA (2019),

“To define cultural diversity, we have to navigate again through a complex web of terms. Some talk about multiculturalism, others about pluriculturalism, and we still have the most appropriate term - interculturality. While the terms “multicultural” and “pluricultural” mean the coexistence and mutual understanding of different cultures in the same society, the term “intercultural” means the interaction between different cultures. This should be the goal of education interested in cultural development. To achieve this goal, education must provide knowledge about the local culture, the culture of various groups that characterize the nation and the culture of other nations (BARBOSA, 2019. p. 15)”.

Therefore, promoting interculturality is the foundation of an education that values diverse and divergent knowledge, without which it is not possible to understand one's own cultural identity.

Virus Graffiti. Diversity. Acrylic on gable, 2018.

ART AND EDUCATION: DECOLONIAL AESTHETICS FOR FEELING, THINKING AND DOING

Decolonial processes have been crossing the various areas of knowledge and it is no different for Education and Art. In these fields, such processes involve the identification of the dynamics of coloniality that formed and instrumentalized this knowledge, finally allowing one to speak of decoloniality, in the sense of removing from the cognitive and emotional formation of other peoples the inculcation of parameters of perception and readings of the world that reinforce coloniality.

First, it was necessary to recognize coloniality in order to formulate its conceptual and practical antidote. This concept was not born in Europe, which previously launched other terms to explain contemporary processes, such as post-modernity or post-coloniality, as early as the 1950s. SALES and CABRERA (2021) point out that the term post-colonial points to two aspects :

the first concerns the decolonization process of the “Third World” countries in the second half of the 20th century and therefore means liberation, emancipation and independence from imperialism and colonialism. The other strand concerns the postcolonial as a broad epistemic, intellectual and political current (SALES; CABRERA, 2021. p. 4).

With the “colonial tour”, from the 1990s, organized by Latin American intellectuals established in the United States, happening in parallel in Latin America, the proposal was then to radicalize the confrontation and criticism in relation to postcolonial studies and post-structuralists, whose arguments continued to be grounded in Eurocentric thinking and which were being aired in Europe.

MIGNOLO (2017) gives a sense of insurgency, or uprising, to the decolonial proposal by affirming not only the crisis of modernity as a universal project of civilization, but pointing out that this project collapsed from the reactive force that emerged in various parts of the world and projecting itself in the production of artists who greatly perceive the power of the image in the construction and

deconstruction of hegemonic thoughts.

The westernization of the world is no longer possible, because more and more people are resisting being integrated into it. On the contrary, people begin to re-exist. This means imagining a way of living their/our lives instead of donating our bodies and our time to corporations, our attention and our intelligence to the insufferable mainstream media, and our energy to banks [...]. Responses of different types and levels have become visible, including the emergence of de-westernization projects [...] (MIGNOLO, 2017, p. 6).

LEÓN (2019), points out that colonial criticism allows understanding the structural relationship between significant practices - which can be discursive, visual or bodily - and resulting global power structures. As it states,

the decolonial critique has its origins in the debate on the matrices of power generated by colonization in the fields of knowledge, culture, representations and in their constant restructuring, along the different waves of modernization and westernization that Latin America has gone through (LEÓN, 2019, p. 61).

For this study, I will use the term decolonial , and with regard to the variation of the prefixes des or de colonial, as explained by QUINTERO, FIGUEIRA E PAZ CONCHA (2019),

There is no consensus regarding the use of the decolonial/decolonial concept, both forms refer to the dissolution of the structures of domination and exploitation configured by coloniality and the dismantling of its main devices. Aníbal Quijano, among others, prefers to refer to decoloniality, while most authors use the idea of decoloniality . According to Catherine Walsh (WALSH, Catherine (org.). Interculturalidad, Estado, sociedad : luchas (de) coloniales of our time . Quito, University Andean Simón Bolívar/ Abya -Yala, 2009), the suppression of the “s” does not mean the adoption of

an anglicism, but the introduction of a difference in the Castilian “des”, as it is not intended only to disarm or undo the colonial (QUINTERO, FIGUEIRA E PAZ CONCHA, 2019. p.16).

From what has been said, it is clear the need to think of ways to remove the exclusivity of the Western perspective, ethnocentered especially in the European continent, and more recently in the North American continent, shifting the gaze to the borders where the diverse sources of references for the formation of the visual repertoire of students in the early years of elementary school, and offering elements for the knowledge and recognition of their own cultural identity from the teaching of Visual Arts. In this regard, HOMI (1989) apud BARBOSA (2019), clarifies that

“1. Identity is being for oneself and for the other; consequently, identity is found among our differences.” 2. The function of the arts in forming the image of identity gives it a characteristic role among the complex aspects of culture. Identification is always the production of “an image of identity and transformation of the subject by assuming or rejecting that image recognized by the other HOMI, 1989. p.139 apud BARBOSA, 2019. pp. 15 and 16”.

It is enough to pay attention to reality to realize that ways of understanding the world are in dispute. One of them focuses on the vision of a single world, another understands it as being multiple, where other worlds are possible beyond the capitalist organization of social life. This directly implies the perception that there are other cultural, artistic and technical manifestations that are legitimate, original and consistent as an expression of unique, different and divergent worldviews, that is, outside the zone of cultural convergence that organizes the world with a single vision.

For GOMEZ (2019), the place where decoloniality can be operationalized is precisely in the field of education, where the arts, humanities and practices, often excluded or placed in reduced spaces, can find a place of creation that is not subordinated to models colonial.

MOURA’s synthesis (2019) explains that

Thinking about a decolonial Art/ Education does not imply delegitimizing knowledge in art from a European perspective (different from a Eurocentric perspective); necessarily implies legitimizing knowledge in Latin American art. It is not a careless and disconnected look that thinks the art and knowledge of this region inserted in Education, but the understanding from the place of enunciation, Latin America, and, through political consciousness, the potentialization of anti-hegemonic and anti- hierarchical in favor of decolonial thinking/doing/being/feeling (MOURA, 2019. p. 33).

It is not, therefore, a question of excluding European or North American art from the students’ visual culture, but of leading to the construction of a broad knowledge about the multiple aesthetics that are constructed in the world and how they are historically structured. The path is to deconstruct colonial references imprinted in the formation of the cultural identity of other peoples with practices that lead to unlearning these inculcations, and this configures the decolonization of minds from a pedagogy understood as a reflective practice of the meaning of being human, as ALBAN puts it (2009). That is, a pedagogy that allows the expression without restrictions, interdictions or belittlement of different cultures, so that we can disarm what restricts our soul. Alongside this, it is worth remembering what Chimananda Adichie (2018) teaches about the importance of the multiplicity of stories that constitute the many references about being in the world and even about what the world is .

Stories matter. Many stories matter. Stories have been used to plunder and slander, but they can also be used to empower and humanize. They can shatter the dignity of a people, but they can also repair that shattered dignity. [...] [...] I would like to end with this idea: when we reject the single story, when we realize that there is never a single story about anywhere, we regain a kind of paradise (ADCHIE, C. p.16, 2018).

In the field of theories, this brief literature

review, introductory and still reduced, allows me to reflectively think about my practices in teaching the Visual Arts. I believe that as a starting point, it is essential to organize a plan capable of being a map to find ways to promote experiences and practical exchanges that mobilize students' interest, enthusiasm and curiosity, while at the same time feeding my teaching practice with new perceptions about the possibilities that give rhythm to learning situations in Art and Culture.

ART, EDUCATION AND CULTURE IN THE GAPS: PLANNING THE TEACHING OF VISUAL ARTS IN A BRAZILIAN CHILDHOOD SCHOOL

Ana Mae Barbosa, since the 1980s, questioned the universality of hegemonic codes in favor of plurality as an articulating principle of knowledge and drew attention to “respect for diversity: diversity of cultural codes; biological diversity, generating expectations of ecological balance; diversity of interpretations and readings of art (BARBOSA, 1998. p.11)”. For her, the key to this transformation lies in education as a place for the development of different cultural codes. In addition, it points out that art in education, as a personal expression and as culture, is an important instrument for cultural identification and the development of perception and imagination, apprehension of the reality of the environment, the development of critical capacity, favoring the analysis perceived reality in order to transform it creatively.

And from this point of view, I consider fundamental a teaching practice that prioritizes art as an element of cultural expression, capable of teaching about the plurality of cultures, considering

that characterize the society or social group, its way of life, its value system, its traditions and beliefs. Art, as a presentational language of the senses, transmits meanings that cannot be

transmitted through any other type of language, such as discursive and scientific languages (BARBOSA, op. cit. p. 16)”.

And beyond that, it is necessary to consider art as an element in the relationship between different cultures and everyday life, not just from the point of view of the aesthetic experience or places of legitimation, such as museums, since these are not universal concepts for all cultures, but as an ethical principle that guides their existence in the world, as the Amerindian peoples do, for example. Thus, the annual planning of the Arts discipline was based on the relationship between the themes of Brazilian art - in their diversity in the times and spaces of the formation of Brazilian culture -, and their visual repertoires (the artistic works themselves) with the contexts (time and space) of their creation, seeking to bring students closer to the biography of the artists, the culture they speak of, their ways of living and producing art, their various techniques, materials and aesthetic expressions. It is important to point out that the planning was oriented in line with the main topics addressed by the regent teachers, especially with regard to topics related to African and Amerindian cultures, making Art activities instruments for the study of other cultural and aesthetic expressions.

ANNUAL PLANNING OF THE DISCIPLINE FOR 2022

Below, I reproduce the menus created for a summary of the discipline's annual planning. As an annex, I provide the weekly table of activities developed. Some photographic records follow on the cover of this work.

Visual Arts quarterly plan 2022 Mar/Apr/May

Composition. Alexandre Mancini, 2016. Above: Multiethnic Mural, detail. Kobra, 2016. Below: Mermaid. Alfredo Volpi, 1960.

Menu: Artistic, aesthetic languages and their knowledge. Art as language. Elements and languages of the visual arts. History of Art to get out of coloniality. Knowledge and development of techniques and materials through artistic practices.

General objective: to present the elements of the languages of the visual arts, continuously involving the interaction between different systems necessary for communication and expression.

Specific objectives: Promoting a non-colonial look at artistic production, making known an overview of the visual arts by exploring the artistic production of Brazilian and foreign painters, sculptors, weavers, engravers, embroiderers, digital artists, designers and illustrators.

Methodology: expository classes from the history of art, placing at the center of the learning process the arts of Latin America, Brazil, its popular culture, but including the relevant productions of Western European art, which are much more available, but not unique for the formation of a thought about art, processes and practices in visual arts and student research.

Jun/Jul/Aug

General objective: to offer from the culture and art of the Jequitinhonha Valley, a place (territory) of

research and knowledge in Popular Art, and to promote from this, the accuracy of the capacity for invention and artistic creation for students. Reaffirm the elements of the visual arts: dots, lines, colors, shapes. Stimulate aesthetic perception in order to expand the visual repertoires about culture. Observe the diversity of Brazilian artistic production.

Menus:

2nd quarter (June to August)

Brazilian Popular Art. Folk Art and Culture. Art or craft? Contemporary Popular Art in Brazil. Artists, languages, materials and techniques of popular art. Above right: Washerwomen. Matizes Dumont. Embroidery.

No author. Next: Flags. Alfredo Volpi. Below: Festa Junina. Detail. Mary Help of Christians. Washerwomen. Heitor de Pleasures.

Objectives: offer subsidies for the construction of knowledge and meanings about popular art and its various forms of expression. Show masters of Brazilian culture and popular art. Favoring the development of aesthetic perception and motor skills through artistic creation activities, expanding the repertoire of references on art production in Brazil.

3rd trimester (September to November)

Upper range: Pieces from the Cooperativa de Artesãos de Campo Alegre and sieve for clay. Intermediate range: Invented Animals from Lira Marques (Araçuaí) and guarantor of the Berilo Community. Bottom band: cotton and Beryl loom. Below: Museum of Frei Chico and Lira Marques in Araçuaí and novels produced in Berilo. Jequitinhonha Valley, 2022.

What is Art? Art as historical and cultural heritage of humanity. Art as a product of history and the multiplicity of human cultures. Art as a language and symbolic system of representation (shapes, lines, colors, planes, symbols, points). Art as resistance. Significant Art Appreciation. Art in its diversity: Latin American arts, African arts, Australian aboriginal arts and Brazilian art. Contemporary aspects since they are alive and reinvent themselves. Colonization and art. Who tells the art story? Brazilian art in relation to European art. Modern art in Brazil. What was the Week of 22?

Above: Congadeiros. Marcio Cintra. Below: African Geometry. No author.

Ta

Objectives: to recognize contents, styles and concepts of Art, gaining tools for artistic making itself. Stimulate students' reflection and favor the understanding of the artistic phenomenon as an object of culture through history and as a set of formal relationships.

ALONG THE WAY

More specifically, and following the teaching interests of the school community globally, the central axis of the Arts discipline was guided by the study of Brazilian popular art produced in the Jequitinhonha Valley, in Minas Gerais, although not exclusively. From the field experience carried out with the artists of the Valley in July 2022, I proposed for the end of the 2nd quarter and beginning of the 3rd quarter, the deepening of experiences of the relationship between history, context and artistic production, developing an affective research with the students, in the sense of affecting them with the discoveries of the trip. For this, I organized the exhibition of pieces of popular art relating them to the history (and image) of the artists who produced them, their contexts, exploring the variety of their techniques and materials. The sequence below describes the themes and their approaches. Some have already been worked on in the different grades according to the age group and their skills and competences, others are still in progress and some points may not be addressed exactly as planned, since the planning is live and can/should be changed from the demands of students and teachers in view of an integrated project of study and learning.

Organizing axes :

1. Living Museum. Sharing information about the art and culture of the Valley, observation and handling of the art pieces brought. Ceramics, tapestry, embroidery, basketry, wood carving and iron sculpture. Artists of the Valley: biography, materials, techniques and artistic production.

2. Ceramics and painting with earth paints in Lira Marques. Imaginary animals inspired by the Animals of My Sertão, by Lira Marques. Studio experiences: Drawing and painting with pastel chalk on special paper. Production of a handmade booklet with images of imaginary animals for the 1st year classes.

3. Earth paints. Studio experiences: painting clay pieces brought from the Valley with earth paint produced by 4th and 5th grade students.

4. The tradition of dolls in D. Izabel, Glória and Andréia (three generations of dollmakers). Modeling exercise of a "doll in the pot", inspired by the popular contemporary work of the artist Andréia, granddaughter of D. Izabel.

5. From cotton to thread, from thread to fabric: spinners and weavers. Handling cotton in the classroom, the natural colors of cotton, plants used to dye yarn. Testimonials by Dona Selma and the weavers of Berilo. Spinning and weaving videos. Photos of the looms and the pieces produced.

6. Embroiderers and threads that tell stories. Atelier experience: drawings from embroidery. Embroider a simple design with elementary stitches: basting. Note: Embroidery needles have well-rounded tips.

SOME FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Utopias aside, these reflections are part of my daily life and I believe that it is even possible to transform mentalities from teaching Art and Culture as decolonial practices. I don't consider it an easy or simple task, but there's nothing left to wait for to promote changes in education, to misalign what is given, bringing to the forefront new symmetries that guarantee the visibility of other essential knowledge for good living.

Supported by theories, concepts, terms and practices that are organized as a counter-discourse, I bet on the political option of decoloniality as an opportune path for education in Latin America, as it was the result of the concerns of Latin American thinkers that emerged in the critique of the binomial modernity/ coloniality, to which all other peoples were subjected and from which they now have the chance to free themselves. And in this sense, I understand the importance of Art and Culture as places of collective social engagement, as instruments of knowledge and recognition of diverse cultural, artistic, aesthetic, ethical and political identities.

From the point of view of my teaching experiences at the Vira Virou school, I have had

a stimulating opportunity to be able to develop the concept, activities and teaching practices with academic freedom, within an environment where there is respect and dialogue, fundamental elements to horizontalize peer relations and ensure that the essentials for thought-provoking, critical and transformative learning situations.

As has been said, the transformations in the teaching of the Arts have brought new challenges to the practices of the school community. This also leads me to think about the specific learning spaces of Art, be it an Art Room or an Atelier, and what is the need for this space for the development of studies, techniques and artistic processes. Is its constitution important from the point of view of more lasting and consistent practical exchanges? To what extent? There are several studies dedicated to this issue, although a more vertical discussion on the subject is not within the scope of this article. But it is worth noting that, similarly to the laboratories constituted for robotics studies, for example, which are legitimate and stimulate scientific and critical thinking so fundamental for a transformative education, it seems quite natural to me that there are spaces constituted for a discipline that deals with processes not always fast, whose techniques and materials are so diverse, as well as the possible didactic resources are multiple. Until when, despite advances in education, will it be necessary to develop this continuous process of building knowledge in adapted environments? What is the priority given to spaces for the continuous development of the Arts in schools? How to create conditions for the formation of a permanent learning space for the arts?

These basic questions, which are discussed in theory but not always materialized in practice, point to the permanence of this utopian topic: ensuring the full existence of a space that meets the needs of research activities and the development of more continuous practices, less interrupted by questions of the limited class time, which allows the prior organization of the tables with materials, which contain a space for drying the produced pieces, which includes some space for the exhibition of the works. I imagine this space as being stimulating, capable of welcoming children's expansiveness and that it is conducive to mediation with students that is less tense and richer from the point of view of learning, experiences and practical exchanges;

where circulation is allowed, where guidance on the activities to be carried out can be efficiently communicated to the student, avoiding wasting time in exhausting repetitions done in high volume and generating more profitable results, serving the theoretical and practical learning of the arts. This is also decolonizing, supporting and legitimizing the field of Art Education within school communities as a territory for training and transforming critical social agents, but at the same time, sensitive ones.

Finally, the theme of this article does not end here and with the objective of expanding this discussion through dialogue with other researchers, this work was enrolled in the V International Seminar on Research in Arts and Visual Culture, in the thematic axis Education, Art and Culture view, which will be promoted by the Federal University of Goiás and Universidad de la Republica Uruguay, and will take place remotely, on December 8th and 9th, 2022.

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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

Organizations began to recognize their direct responsibility in relation to social problems and adopt actions to address them. The contemporary definition of CSR includes the company's commitment to society and humanity, based on accountability for its performance, considering the use of resources that do not belong to it. Terms such as corporate citizenship and corporate governance were also introduced, highlighting the need for socially responsible and sustainable practices in the long term. Where values and ethical issues can go beyond "profit". In this scenario, the ability to make effective decisions is fundamental to the success and survival of organizations. By adopting an ethical stance, companies strengthen their reputation and build a relationship of trust. Analyzing social delimitations, the issue of ethics that incorporates such actions, and how such a movement emerges in the face of companies in Brazil.

KEYWORDS : Responsibility; Citizenship; Need; Resources; Decisions.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of civilization throughout history has been marked by continuous processes of transformation. According to Oliveira (2013), a change of significant proportions triggered by the Industrial Revolution caused profound changes, where there was a notable transformation in production systems, boosting manufacturing activities and generating substantial impacts on the economy, social standards and, inevitably, the environment. .

Concern about the ramifications of this development model gained prominence following the publication, in 1972, of the report "Limits to Growth" by the Club of Rome. This report warned of population expansion, agricultural production, industrial production, use of natural resources and pollution as driving factors for growth, but also as limiting factors if they were not properly controlled. Concern about the consequences of this growth model grew on an international scale, leading the United Nations (UN) to introduce the issue on the global agenda, with the aim of seeking development that minimized the negative effects. Thus, the Sustainable Development proposal emerged, launched in 1987 based on the Brundtland Report . This development model aims to balance social, economic and environmental needs, with the aim of ensuring the sustainability of natural resources and the planet.

In this context, companies, industries and various productive sectors are called upon to adapt, whether due to legal impositions, the pressure of society's demands or consumer awareness. This call gave rise to the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

However, also when delimiting the ethical issue that involves a business, which can be linked to the moral principles of companies, in this sense acted as guidelines for how a company conducts itself in its operations. In many ways, the same guidelines that individuals use to behave acceptably in personal and professional settings also apply to businesses. When acting ethically, be in a way that determines what is "right" and what is "wrong".

CSR has a substantial impact on company operations and performance. In this sense, it is justified to

understand these implications as a way to improve the efficiency, competitiveness and sustainability of organizations.

The objective of this article is to understand the tangible aspects that can promote and understand CSR in Brazilian companies. Analyzing social delimitations, the issue of ethics that incorporates such actions, and how such a movement emerges in the face of companies in Brazil.

Given the above, how can Corporate Social Responsibility impact the socioeconomic development of companies in Brazil?

The research method is based on the form of bibliographical research, which according to Gil (2012) helps guide the search, providing guidelines and relevant keywords related to the topic of interest. With this, words were defined that could help in the context relevant to the topic, thus researched on: Corporate Social Responsibility; Corporate Environmental Responsibility; Sustainability; Sustainability in companies; Sustainability Tripods; Sustainable Companies; Business ethics; Ethics Socio-environmental; Environmental awareness; Corporate social responsibility; Sustainable practices in organizations.

Data collection was done entirely on the internet, both on Google and Google Scholar, as a way of delimiting a tool with the same database, in this sense, better aggregating the research based on the keywords listed. From the perspective of temporal construction, the publications had a long order over the years, starting in 1970 until 2023.

DEVELOPMENT

Corporate Social Responsibility

According to Dias (2011), the notion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) began to develop in response to these growing social demands for greater environmental responsibility and an improvement in society's quality of life. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, known as Rio/92, highlighted the importance of companies in unsustainable development and emphasized the need for ethical and responsible

standards, SA 8000, AHSAS 18001, AA 1000, the Earth Charter, the Millennium Goals and Targets, the UN Global Compact, ILO Conventions, Ethos Social Responsibility Indicators and the GRI (Global Reporting initiatives).

The duality of the company as an economic and social entity is highlighted, since, while it seeks to obtain profits, it also has social functions defined by the State, in accordance with ethical principles established in the Federal Constitution of 1988. In this context, the Federal Constitution establishes general principles of economic activity, aimed at promoting a dignified existence and social justice. The company as a social institution has the primary responsibility of producing goods and providing services to meet the needs of society, distributing wealth through the creation of jobs and contributing taxes to national development. Failure to comply with these social functions may result in punishments as provided for in legislation. For Ashley (2002), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) requires a new approach for companies, including a new mental model for social, economic and political relations. She highlights that CSR should not be limited to a social dimension of the company, but rather seen as part of an integrative vision that encompasses the social, economic and environmental dimensions.

Neto and Froes (2001) argue that CSR involves management that encompasses both internal and external audiences, including active participation in the community. They emphasize that the concept of social responsibility is part of a broader concept, sustainable development.

Mebrato (1998) characterizes CSR as a process that encompasses reputation, ethics and governance, with the objective of minimizing social exclusion. It highlights the importance of considering CSR in relation to sustainable development and taking into account stakeholder expectations.

ISO 26000, launched in 2010, defines CSR as the organization's responsibility for the impacts of its decisions and activities on society and the environment. This includes ethical and transparent behavior that contributes to sustainable development and is consistent with international standards of behavior.

According to Neto and Froes (2001), the concept of

CSR goes beyond legal compliance and philanthropy. CSR is seen as an effort by organizations to curb actions that could harm society or the environment. In this sense, it encompasses citizen responsibility by defining rights, duties and attitudes that generate value for everyone, covering both individuals and legal entities.

Carroll (1979), highlights a range of economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic obligations. Economic responsibility is the foundation of all other dimensions of CSR, and companies must balance profit with obedience to laws, ethics and corporate citizenship. Carroll's pyramid illustrates the four dimensions of CSR, emphasizing that economic performance is the foundation of all other responsibilities.

In this sense, the author points out that the development of companies is intrinsically linked to economic growth, while for others, this relationship is not so close. This development model has the fundamental objective of aligning economic growth with the responsible use of natural resources, environmental protection and concern for social well-being. This approach does not exclude economic growth from development, but it also does not attribute all the merit to the economic aspect. Instead, it seeks an alignment between the two, incorporating two additional dimensions, the ecological-environmental and the social.

This vision of development with an emphasis on social and environmental dimensions began to gain strength in the 1960s. The release of the Club of Rome report in 1972, entitled "The Limits to Growth," and the UN Conference on the Human Environment held in the same year in Stockholm, Sweden, scored crucial points. However, the consolidation of the concept of Sustainable Development only occurred in 1992, during the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted, establishing 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) based on the Millennium Development Goals launched in 2000. Thus, by addressing issues such as poverty eradication, gender equality, health, education, reduction of inequalities, climate action, life in water and on land, among others, with the aim of ensuring sustainable development

feasibility, these concepts share several common characteristics and principles that make them relevant in the context of sustainable development. In a complementary way, when observing what Ashley (2002) highlights; Aligrelli (2011); Alves et al. (2015), the convergence between Ecodevelopment and Sustainable Development, based on the aspects: Holistic view: Both concepts consider development as a complex system that involves interactions between different components, recognizing that the economy, society and the environment are intrinsically linked.

Criticism of economic reductionism: Both eco-development and Sustainable Development question the excessive emphasis on economic growth as the only measure of progress, emphasizing the need to evaluate development based on multiple indicators and dimensions.

Long-term vision: Both concepts consider the implications of development on future generations, promoting the notion that sustainable development must meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Social well-being: Both are concerned with the well-being of communities and seek to reduce social inequalities, promoting a fairer distribution of the benefits of development.

Environmental dimension: They recognize the importance of preserving the environment as an integral part of the development process, promoting the responsible use of natural resources and the minimization of negative environmental impacts. Management of renewable resources: Both eco-development and Sustainable Development advocate the responsible management of natural resources, considering their capacity for regeneration and renewability.

Respect for nature's time: Both concepts value respect for nature's natural cycles, recognizing that the unrestrained exploitation of resources can result in irreversible damage.

Favoring the local and global plan: Both emphasize the importance of promoting sustainable development at local and global levels, recognizing that specific solutions and strategies may vary

according to the characteristics of each region.

Given these aspects, the authors address these similarities, eco-development and Sustainable Development, as a common approach to development that seeks to balance economic, social and environmental dimensions. The importance of covering these three dimensions is fundamental to guarantee truly sustainable development, which meets the needs of the present without compromising the future, respecting the interconnection between economy, society and the environment. This three-dimensional perspective can be fundamental to building a more equitable and environmentally responsible future.

The ethics of Social Responsibility in Companies

The issue that emerges from the ethical issue in companies involves a type of Corporate Social Responsibility, which can be a recognition that a company, corporation or business organization has social, cultural and environmental responsibilities towards the community in which it seeks to operate. This type of corporate citizenship involves an organization accepting the need to better fulfill its responsibilities in order to establish and maintain sustainable success for the organization.

According to Chiavenato (1999), social responsibility is an approach in which companies recognize their impact on society and seek to mitigate this negative impact, while at the same time contributing positively to the sustainable development of the communities in which they operate. For the author, many companies adopt social responsibility practices to not only achieve their own objectives, but also as a way of giving back to society and meeting the ethical and moral expectations of the community in general.

According to Sant'Anna (2015), in recent years there have been changes in the commitment to corporate social responsibility, which indicates:

Requirements at a business level are changing, a few years ago, some companies said they acted responsibly and ethically, now, they cannot just talk about it, it is necessary to put it into practice or they will be punished. Stakeholders do not just accept a logo or a seal indicating that the company

transparency.

According to Neto and Froes (2001), some of the central elements of citizenship do not seem to apply directly to corporations. For example, “citizenship” typically implies membership of a state and an identity similar to national identity; but this connotation of citizenship is obviously problematic for corporations. However, the language of citizenship helps focus our attention on various legal and political virtues of corporations—topics that have been largely neglected by discussions under other headings, such as CSR or sustainability. Garcia (1999), highlights that the ethics of responsibility is related to business ethics, highlighting the importance of considering the social consequences of business actions and decisions. The author points out that the ethics of responsibility requires companies to foresee and consider the possible consequences of their actions, respecting current moral and ethical precepts, as opposed to the ethics of ultimate purposes, which seeks exclusively profit, regardless of social consequences.

According to Ashley (2002), ethics stands out with the need for companies to consider the consequences of their actions in the exploitation of natural resources and the importance of preserving the environment. This not only has a cost, but also represents a fundamental duty, since the environment is a fundamental right for everyone. In this sense, the author signals awareness and changes in business behavior in relation to environmental preservation can lead to a revolution in the behavior of all companies, promoting a more responsible and sustainable approach.

Neto and Froes (2001), point out that the environment as a fundamental right and a fundamental duty, it is essential to promote awareness and responsibility, sharing the burden of preserving the environment and, at the same time, reducing inequalities in the competitive capacity between responsible and non-responsible companies. This approach emphasizes the importance of ethical and environmental responsibility for companies in the search for a fairer and more sustainable society.

Corporate social responsibility is a concept that is based on the idea that companies have a role beyond the simple objective of making a profit; they also have a commitment to society and the environment in which they operate.

In this context, ethical conduct in companies plays

a fundamental role in building solid corporate social responsibility. Business ethics are not limited to compliance with legal standards, but go further, encompassing the adoption of behaviors that benefit society and the environment. Companies that act ethically not only follow the laws, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of their actions.

Corporate social responsibility encompasses the notion that companies must act in a way that benefits the community in which they operate. This includes practices such as creating jobs, paying taxes, promoting social causes and preserving the environment. When companies adopt ethical conduct, they contribute significantly to achieving these objectives.

Corporate Social Responsibility in Brazil

According to Guimaraes (1984), CSR is based on the premise that organizations have direct responsibility and the ability to address social problems. For the author, companies are not only economic entities, but they also play a role in improving the living conditions of society.

Rico (1998), introduces the concept of corporate citizenship, which goes beyond fulfilling the company’s economic function. The author highlights that corporate citizenship presupposes that the company is co-responsible for the well-being of the community.

Soutello Alves (2001) defines corporate citizenship as a set of principles and management systems aimed at creating or preserving value for society. This concept involves the development of socially responsible management methods that meet society’s desires.

According to Soutello Alves (2001), with a corporate-citizen culture, companies assume commitment and define policies in relation to their partners. It practices a set of values that preserve and respect the interests of the parties with which it has a direct and indirect relationship. According to the author, these companies are proactive in the search for solutions to social problems, mobilizing resources in various ways, such as information, management techniques and financial resources.

According to Reis (2007), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Brazil gained prominence throughout the 1990s, which was driven by the country’s redemocratization and economic opening,

to Sales (2012), the development of CSR actions is also rooted in philanthropic initiatives that some companies previously carried out, and these benevolent activities continue to be an important part of the concept.

According to Camargo et al. (2002), the creation of institutions such as the ABRINQ Foundation for the Rights of Children and Adolescents, the Brazilian Association of Businessmen for Citizenship (CIVES) and the Ethos Institute played significant roles in promoting CSR in the country. For Sartore (2012), the creation of the Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE) on the São Paulo Stock Exchange in 2005 and the inclusion of social responsibility metrics in business rankings demonstrate the growing importance of CSR in the Brazilian business context.

Sartore (2012), points out that although the CSR adoption model in Brazil is different from the process in the United States, with a greater focus on the inclusion of philanthropic actions, it is evident that the synergy of several factors and events contributed to the strengthening and dissemination of CSR practices in the country.

The concepts of CSR in Brazil, the Ethos Institute established a widely adopted definition, which defines it as “the form of management that is defined by the company’s ethical and transparent relationship with all the publics with which it interacts and by the establishment of goals businesses that drive the sustainable development of society, preserving environmental and cultural resources for future generations, respecting diversity and promoting the reduction of social inequalities” (Instituto Ethos, 2009). However, according to Reis (2009), there are several different interpretations and approaches to CSR in Brazil, including social action, private social investment, corporate philanthropy, corporate governance and social responsibility. For the author, these diverse approaches reflect the different ways in which companies in Brazil approach CSR, from philanthropic actions to a commitment to promoting sustainable development and reducing social inequalities.

CONCLUSION

Given the scenario that we see the importance of responsibility in companies, seen within the spectrum of CSR, in which over time, highlighting its roots, the growing awareness of the need for ethical and responsible business practices and the convergence of different approaches and concepts related to the topic.

However, an explanation of how the notion of CSR emerged in response to growing social demands for greater environmental responsibility and improvements in society’s quality of life. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, Rio/92, emphasized the importance of companies in sustainable development and the need for ethical and responsible practices.

He also highlights the duality of companies, which must not only seek profit, but also have social functions defined by the State and ethical principles. Failure to fulfill these social functions may result in legal punishments.

The CSR approach has developed over time, incorporating several frameworks, including documents such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the OECD Guidelines for Multinationals, ISO standards and other initiatives. This demonstrates the growing awareness of the importance of the social, economic and environmental dimensions of CSR.

The relationship between eco-development and Sustainable Development is explored, emphasizing the importance of a holistic, long-term vision, social well-being and responsible management of natural resources. These approaches seek to balance economic growth with environmental preservation and social justice.

Ethics plays a central role in CSR, encouraging companies to consider the social and environmental consequences of their actions. In addition to complying with laws, ethical companies adopt practices that benefit society and the environment. By observing the evolution of CSR in Brazil, highlighting the influence of institutions such as the Ethos Institute, the development of corporate sustainability indices and different interpretations of CSR, including social action, philanthropy and commitment to sustainable development. Be how companies that adopt stronger CSR practices can

to the authors' understanding, if it is approached as a genuine commitment to ethical and responsible business practices. Companies seeking long-term benefits from CSR often integrate these principles into their corporate culture and strategy.

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ICT LEGISLATION IN EDUCATION AND THE USE OF ICT IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to discuss the legislation that addresses the use of information and communication technologies in education and the use of these TICs in elementary school. We verified the use of technology in our daily lives, and we also observed that this use has already expanded into schools, but we know that there are advantages and difficulties regarding its use. In addition, we sought to know, in this study, which laws address the use of these TICs in education. For this, we opted for a documentary and bibliographic study, with a search for the most recent literature and renowned authors who address the topic, using a qualitative approach with document analysis based on Cellard (2008). In the results, it was possible to highlight some legislation that had greater prominence regarding the use of TICs. It was also possible to know the main obstacles faced to insert TICs in schools, such as: difficulties for teachers, physical structure, maintenance of equipment. In addition, we highlight the advantages of using ICTs, such as improved teaching and learning, easier class planning by teachers, more creative and dynamic classes, closer relations between people and the possibility of educating regardless of place. We conclude that despite all the barriers presented, the advantages are very beneficial and provide a breadth in the student's view of the world.

Keywords— Education. Legislation. TICs

INTRODUCTION

From globalization, a great technological advance in all areas of knowledge has been observed in the world. Likewise, this technological advance has also been observed in the area of education, what we call Information and Education Technology - ICTs, which play an increasingly important role in the way we communicate, learn and live.

These are defined as a group of technologies that assist in communication, including hardware, such as smartphones and microcomputers, software, with messaging or teleconferencing applications, and everything else that can be accessed through data access networks, such as the internet. .

The use of information technology can be verified in our daily lives, being increasingly present and people increasingly dependent on them. Today, almost everyone has access to a cell phone or a computer. Therefore, this technological innovation provides the use of modern teaching resources at school, aiming at improving teaching and learning.

This progress in information technologies allowed the creation of tools that can be used by teachers in the classroom, providing greater availability of information and resources for the educator, promoting a more dynamic, efficient and innovative educational process. Therefore, the use of these technological tools in education must be understood as a new teaching methodology, which allows greater digital interaction between the educator and the student.

In addition, the arrival of ICTs in schools generated great advantages for the teaching and learning of students, but also brought several challenges in relation to their use.

However, for the use of these technologies in schools, there was the creation of a legal apparatus for their regulation, such as several laws, decrees, resolutions, among others.

RESEARCH METHOD

Thus, the step to be taken was the choice of the theme that addresses Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in education,

the next step was the planning for carrying out the research that was elaborated through the research project.

The present study focuses on the investigation of ICTs in education, thus using a qualitative approach.

As for the type of research, it will use a qualitative approach, which according to Guerra (2014) takes into account that human beings are not passive and continually interpret the world in which they live. In this way, the qualitative study has as its objective the human being.

Thus, the research will have a qualitative approach of an exploratory nature, as it aims to provide more information on the subject to be investigated.

According to Selltiz et al. (1987), this type of study includes those that aim to discover ideas and intuitions, in an attempt to acquire greater familiarity with the researched phenomenon. In this type of study there is no need to formulate hypotheses.

The techniques chosen for the collection of data used the bibliographical research where the search for the literature that approaches the ICTs in the practice of the education was made, where it was looked for the reality of the use of the ICTs in the schools, in its daily life, verifying its advantages and its difficulties.

Another technique chosen was document analysis. In the documental analysis, documents related to legislation that address the use of ICTs, including those aimed at education, were sought.

The same technique was performed using the search for literature relevant to the topic, ICTs in education, with a search on scientific literature search sites: Scielo, Google Scholar, Capes Periodical.

SEARCH RESULTS

In Brazilian Constitutional Law, it is possible to identify a reference regarding education and technology. Since education is a fundamental social right, guaranteed in arts. 6 and 205 of the Magna Carta. However, we also verified that the

constitution stipulates that the National Education Plan must articulate the national education system, through collaborative means, through integrated actions of the public authorities that lead to the humanistic, scientific and technological promotion of the Country (CF, art. 214, V).

However, it was in Law 9394/1996, the Law of Guidelines and Bases for National Education, that the use of Information and Communication Technologies in education was highlighted. LDBEN establishes the guidelines and bases of national education.

Article 32 of LDBEN (Law 9394/1996) defines the objectives of Brazilian Elementary Education, which is the basic education of citizens.

I – the development of the ability to learn, having as basic means the full mastery of reading, writing and calculation;

II – understanding the natural and social environment, the political system, technology, the arts and the values on which society is based;

III – the development of learning capacity, with a view to acquiring knowledge and skills and forming attitudes and values;

IV – the strengthening of family bonds, the bonds of human solidarity and reciprocal tolerance on which social life is based. Soon after the LDBEN, in 1997, through Ordinance nº 522 of the MEC, the National Program for Informatics in Education - PROINFO was created, which sought to introduce informatics technology in the public education network, more specifically in elementary and high school.

PROINFO works together with the Educational Technology Nuclei - NTE, which are nuclei composed of professors and professionals in the area of technology and aim to train professionals to work in this technological educational field, in addition to transforming educators as multipliers of knowledge in this nucleus (BRAZIL, 1997).

Estevão and Passos (2015, p. 201) highlight the objectives of the program:

1) Improve the quality of the teaching-learning

process;

2) Enable the creation of a new cognitive ecology in school environments through adequate incorporation of new information technologies by schools;

3) To provide an education focused on scientific and technological development;

4) Educating for global citizenship in a technologically developed society

Decree 6300, which provides for PROINFO, highlights that its main objectives are:

a) the promotion of the pedagogical use of information and communication technologies in basic education schools in urban and rural public education networks;

b) fostering the improvement of the teaching and learning process, with the use of technologies;

c) training of educational agents involved in the Program's actions (BRASIL, 2007, p. 1).

The counterpart of local governments (municipalities and state governments) for joining the program is to provide the infrastructure for schools, which is essential for them to receive computers.

Figure 1 - Institutional and organizational design of ProInfo.

Source: Estevão e Passos (2015).

Basniak and Soares (2016) state that, despite the implementation of ProInfo, it was implemented more than twenty years ago, helping in the distribution of equipment to public schools, in

training, and having led teachers to reflect on their pedagogical practice and the need for change, effective digital inclusion in the school environment has not yet been evidenced.

Also, according to Oliveira et al. (2009) the training provided by ProInfo has been providing a rethinking of teachers regarding pedagogical practice. The authors observed these transformations through the Introduction to Digital Education course, where new paths were traced in order to favor digital inclusion, thus improving the dynamics regarding the use of Educational Informatics Laboratories.

Alonso (2010) highlights that distance education is considered a teaching modality that allows for an increase in number and possibilities of access to education for an increasing portion of the population.

Maddalena comments on the growth of distance education and its regulation in terms of higher education.

[...] it can be said that the modality grew faster than its regulation and as a consequence, today we have courses and some higher education proposals that do not follow the fundamental and essential bases of Public Universities, currently there are many courses that respond to market interests and international organizations that do not bring quality proposals and are often not in line with our Latin American reality. (MADDALENA, 2012, p.1)

However, all this technological advance that invaded the world community did not occur in an integral and homogeneous way. There are still individuals who do not fully participate in this new scenario and still live on the margins of social practices carried out by digital means.

Moran (2009) highlights other problems related to this technological change at school, as he states that many schools present themselves more in a traditional than innovative way in relation to school culture. The author also states that teacher-focused teaching is still predominant, rather than a focus on teaching and learning.

This adequate management for the use of ICTs

is an important fact that is usually pointed out by teachers, mainly from public schools, as there are usually technologies available in the school, however, they lack maintenance or internet to allow access to students. contents.

Rendimento educacional - Brasil

Aprendizado dos alunos no ensino remoto com relação ao esperado no presencial*

Engajamento dos alunos da rede estadual no ensino médio remoto em 2020

*Independentemente da idade e da série.
Fonte: Insper e Instituto Unibanco

Source: <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/infomaterias/2021/07/pandemia-acentua-deficit-educacional-e-exige-aco-es-do-poder-publico#gallery-1>

According to UNESCO, in March 2021, a year after the beginning of the pandemic, almost half of the students in the world feel affected by the partial or total closure of schools, and they still estimate that more than 100 million extra children will be proficient in reading. below the minimum level as a result of this health emergency. Given this scenario, it is necessary to prioritize the recovery of Education, in order to avoid a catastrophe that will affect this entire generation.

Jovens que já pensaram em desistir dos estudos durante a pandemia

Distribuição por faixa etária em 2020

Distribuição por faixa etária em 2021

Source: <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/infomaterias/2021/07/pandemia-acentua-deficit-educacional-e-exige-acoes-do-poder-publico#gallery-1>

Research shows that education and income go hand in hand. Thus, this drop in learning indicators may result in great financial loss in the near future, for students and for Brazil, as recognized by the Federal Government.

The pandemic scenario brought reflections and concerns to the educational area, as Martins (2020, p. 251) addresses “[...] the working conditions of teachers, the quality of the teaching-learning process, the relevance and meaning of topics to be addressed, the development of student-centered pedagogical practices [...]”. With this, there is a need to give voice to teachers of regular Basic Education classrooms, in order to understand their perception of the pandemic moment in relation to education and the challenges to their pedagogical practice.

CONCLUSION

The present study addressed the legislation regarding Information and Communication Technologies in schools, also highlighting the obstacles regarding its implementation and the advantages regarding its use in schools.

It was possible to know the main laws that address ICTs in education, where the mention of the theme can be observed from the Magna letter that mentions the creation of a fair society entering the scientific and technological incentive, the LDBEN that highlights that education must promote the preparation of the student and his qualification for work, since today we live in a technological environment on a daily basis. We commented on the Proinfo program that sought to introduce IT technology into the public education network, We approached the legislation that institutes EAD-type education and finally we cite Resolution No. that we live

We highlight the main obstacles to the integration of ICTs in education, where we can mention the difficulty of assimilating technologies by locations, age group, the difficulty of adapting the teacher, thus requiring continued education on the subject, the lack of maintenance of equipment in schools, the lack of internet, the constant change in technology,

the constant volume of data on the internet and the resignification of the teacher’s role in the face of technology .

It was also possible to identify that the pandemic period promoted a hastily apprehension of ICTs by schools, but this did not occur in an integral way, since several schools did not resume activities, due to various obstacles.

We point out the advantages of including ICTs in schools as new ways of learning, facilitating the planning of activities, making classes more dynamic and creative for students, providing new means of interaction, also providing greater access to information, greater social interaction and allows the reduction of prejudice. We also point out the advantages in relation to EAD teaching that allows education to go beyond the walls of the school, allowing the student to have access to education anywhere, just by having access to the internet.

In addition to this range of advantages, the fact that ICTs promotes more cooperative learning is also highlighted, making thinking more critical and creative, inducing the student to meet new patterns of relationship, challenge rules and promote innovation and distinction.

We also verified that the emergency remote teaching that has been used in the pandemic period we are experiencing, allowed the continuity of school education, for the schools that joined it.

But we emphasize that the use of ICTs helps in promoting a more democratic school and promoting transformative actions that allow the student to see the world beyond the walls of the school.

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KNOWLEDGE, KNOW HOW TO TEACH: REFLECTIONS FOR A DECOLONIAL EDUCATION IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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FEMALE VOICES

Conceição Evaristo

My great-grandmother's voice
echoed as a child in the holds of the ship. It echoed the wails of a lost childhood.

My grandmother's voice
echoed obedience to the whites who own everything.

My mother's voice
echoed in a rebellious whisper in the back of other people's kitchens, under the bundles of dirty clothes worn by white people along the dusty road to the favela.

My voice still
echoes perplexing verses with rhymes of blood and hunger.

My daughter's voice collects all our voices collects in her mute silent voices choked in her throat. My daughter's voice collects in her speech and action. Yesterday – today – now. -freedom.

TEACHER

Before starting work on the experiences of the Pre 1 group, I would like to make a brief account of my journey to this space and my process of building racial literacy.

I graduated in pedagogy from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. During my training, I participated in the study and research group on Anti-Racist Education (GEPEAR/UFRJ) and this period was more than a deepening in the search for racial awareness to promote a decolonial education, it was also a time of discovery, of self-reflection and bringing to light pains not even revealed yet.

Since I was a little girl, I was reminded, almost daily, by my mother, that I had one foot in the slave quarters, I realized that there was much more than one member in this place of suffering. Throughout my research and debates, I had tears unveiled when I made unpalatable discoveries, sleepless nights after realizing the lack of information about my origin and 'starts' that past episodes were not "accidentally" or "coincidences", and so, in addition to expanding reflections, I became aware of the impacts of racism in the school space, both in acts committed by children, often in a joking tone, and in acts committed by people who should be committed to annihilating this type of practice.

Silvio de Almeida, author of the book *Structural Racism* (2019) says that:

"Institutions are just the materialization of a social structure or a mode of socialization that has racism as one of its organic components. Put more bluntly: institutions are racist because society is racist."

After this awakening, I started to pay attention to the proposed projects, characters, and professional references brought to be presented to the children. For most of my training period, I was in small children's classrooms and this made my thinking conditioned to the reception of early childhood education. With this, some questions arise:

- How to bring such delicate topics to the conversation circles?

- How to promote dialogue without bringing guilt

and causing mental confusion to white children?

- How to propose an anti-racist walk from early childhood education?

These doubts are always with me and keep me researching and reflecting on the most appropriate way to approach and bring such a sensitive and important topic to children, to continue promoting egalitarian education.

In the search for an anti-racist and more critical practice on various topics, I began to desire a workspace that would allow for such reflections and that would promote debates on the need to break with practices rooted in our history. Along the way, I found *Vira-virus*, which is a school that enables continuous debates about our daily work and places itself as a space that values different cultures, consequently enabling the broadening of the eyes of both teachers and students and those responsible for influences in the construction of Brazilian culture, which means valuing the culture of native peoples, standing out in this context, indigenous and African.

After my journey, I begin my journey with the Pre 1 group from here, recalling an excerpt from the opinion of Law 10.639/03 on the importance of pedagogies that value the history and contribution of black people to the development of Brazilian culture:

"Pedagogies to combat racism and discrimination designed to educate positive ethnic/racial relations aim to strengthen black consciousness among blacks and awaken black consciousness among whites. Among blacks, they will be able to offer knowledge and security to be proud of their African origin; for whites, it may allow them to identify the influences, contribution, participation, and importance of black history and culture in their way of being, living, relating to other people, notably black people. They will also be part of a process of recognition, by the State, society, and the school, of the social debt they owe to the black segment of the population, enabling an explicit position to be taken against racism and racial discrimination

and the construction of affirmative actions in the different teaching levels of Brazilian education.” (GONÇALVES E SILVA, 2004, p.10).

BEFORE THE START

This work is not about exposing a project developed in the Pre 1 class, but rather a reflection on the need for and importance of an attentive and conscious teaching practice, which I sought to explore in this year of 2022 with the group.

Throughout the year I tried to remain vigilant so that the moments of planning the proposals did not fail to contain a reflection on how to include significant references and could contemplate and value Afro culture. Believing that we should not wait for a theme or a “commemorative” date to appear to work on the history and contribution of African peoples in the construction of our culture, I reiterate that the process is continuous and continues to be present in the routine of the Pre 1 whenever I post the possibility of insertion.

Part of the first experiences with racism occurs at school and in early childhood education. It is essential to recognize that children see differences and can verbalize them. When we observe comparative comments about bodies, hair, skin, and other characteristics, such as phenotypic, children are making it clear that they realize that we are not all the same, as some people say, and end up silencing debates that could contribute to the deconstruction of racist practices. Therefore, we teachers need to make it clear that there is no problem with plurality, whatever the sphere, quite the contrary. By bringing heterogeneity as enriching, we strengthen black and white children. We tend to think that race is just about black people, as if “white” isn’t race either. Dialogue about racism is indispensable as it impacts the development of identity construction, as reflected by philosopher Djamila.

“ In a society like the Brazilian one, with a slavery heritage, black people will experience racism from the place of those who are the object of this oppression, from the place that restricts opportunities because of this system of oppression. So

both groups can and should discuss these issues, but they will speak from different places.” (Ribeiro, 2017, p. 86)

People are not born racist, but with the reproduction of certain patterns throughout life, an “anti-black” movement spreads, a look where everything that belongs to whites is validated and what comes from blacks is inferior. And so, black people are weakening and looking for alternatives to be accepted in a society that is exempt from the problem daily.

A white child grows and develops surrounded by references that help build self-esteem. On TV, in literature, in toys that fill store shelves, and in cartoons. There is a very thick layer of representations that place the image of white people as a standard, correct, beautiful figure, and for the irreprehensible to exist, there must be a lack of form. We then find black children growing up with numerous gaps in this process of building a framework, since it is not possible to come across figures that help them to represent the projections of their dreams.

Although we walk in a crescent, it is not the rule to find characters valued by childhood with dark skin, curly hair, and well-marked features and this creates a distance between black bodies and their ancestry, causing a conflicting relationship with their blackness. In an interview for the national early childhood network, Ana Oliva, a psychologist and master in education and social justice, talks about the importance of representativeness in childhood:

“ Childhood, especially early childhood (0 to 6 years old) is central to the subject’s development. It is in early childhood that the child builds the basic skills of a human being (walking, talking, symbolizing). It is also a stage of building bonds, identity, and self-esteem. It is in this phase that the subject will build his bases for the relationship with himself and with others. Therefore, diversity, representativeness, identity, and culture are central discussions for the promotion of rights and the construction of subjectivity in childhood .”

Along my trajectory, between internships and conducting, I was able to be inside some middle-class schools in the city of Rio and the truth is that it is not common to find black students in these spaces, since the black population finds it very difficult to achieve such status. My arrival at Vira-Virou was full of pleasant surprises. Unfortunately, it is still not possible for us to say that 1/3 of our school's school community is made up of brown or black people, but I still consider it a space where it is possible to see the presence of black children and families more frequently than in other environments and I think that doesn't say enough about our school. I see this coming and going as a portrait of a place heading toward historical deconstruction.

I remember the first days when I arrived at Vira and saw some black students with long, colorful braids. I was surprised, happy, and excited at the same time. I had just arrived at a school that I already admired and saw as a reference in promoting Brazilian popular culture, but I did not expect to find black children so comfortable in an environment where it is notably composed of a white majority. That caught my attention and made me think that in addition to promoting and valuing popular culture, it would also be a possible place to debate racial issues.

Despite already being related to research in favor of anti-racist education, I felt more encouraged to remain in the search for knowledge to further broaden my view and teach feelings and experiences experienced by me, which could contribute to the group. For Maria Lúcia da Silva, a member of the AMMA Psique e Negritude institute, "thinking about the psychic effects of racism is thinking about it as a structuring element of society, but also of the perceptions of affections and the way of thinking about the world". In this sense, I have placed myself as an instrument of transformation, however difficult it may be at times since I suffer daily and direct impacts from this society that I denounce and fight.

This year I had the pleasure of visiting the Museu Afro Brasil, located in Ibirapuera Park in the city of São Paulo. There were so many memories, so much richness and so many discoveries that I went back to school bubbling with desires. After this visit, without a doubt, my speech intensified,

my relationships expanded and my desire to bring different knowledge to children increased.

I started to do more searches for places that could provide me with information to add to my work. I visited the Quilombo Cafundá Astrogilda, which is located in Vargem Grande, very close to our school, I did the African heritage circuit with the Pretos Novos Institute in downtown Rio and since then I have been on the path of research and investigation.

THE YEAR 2022 WITH THE PRE 1 CLASS.

Throughout the school term, it was thought to work on themes such as Afro culture and its contributions to our culture in a very organic way, after all, it is not about canceling white culture and making learning conditional on black knowledge. As previously stated, anti-racist education should not be present only in projects to bring the possibility of debating isolated episodes or on the 20th of November. The construction of a racial conscience takes place daily, especially in a country like Brazil, structurally racist and denialist in this sense, since we recognize the existence of racism, but if questioned about our conventions, most people exempt themselves from attitudes that would be easily questionable. Silvio de Almeida says:

“ Societal change is not only achieved through denunciations or the moral repudiation of racism: it depends, above all, on taking positions and adopting anti-racist practices ” (2019, p. 52)

Considering this thought, the experiences thought and proposed for the group were permeated by figures, symbols, and materialities that could contribute to the fight against racism and its impacts in the school context without requiring dense or delicate conversations for the group that has children between 4 and 5 years. The materials

brought were offered lightly, but without forgetting to talk about their origins and their contributions to society.

Drawing parallels between Brazilian legends and African legends, it was possible to bring to the conversation circles countless similarities between our stories, characters, and scenarios and the group was able to expand its repertoire also through research carried out with the family. Throughout the year we receive contributions of materials that were collected by the family after the child took some report of experience experienced at school. It was common for us to receive photos, texts, poems, drawings made collectively, books, and the like.

Among the many known legends, the Legend of the Baobab caught the attention of children. With interest intensifying, I acquired tools so that we could delve deeper and I took the opportunity to work on territoriality, through observation of the world map and conversations about how far we are from the African continent, it was possible to get to know the book “O Velho Baobá” and think under what conditions these trees arrived in Brazil, we discovered that this tree can also offer us a fruit called ‘MUKUA’ which is commonly used in culinary dishes to add vitamins and minerals to meals. On a visit to Porto de Galinhas, student Helena Paciello registered Baobás at the hotel where she stayed. Those responsible sent us the photos through the class app to share with the class. It was a joy to realize the presence of Baobabs in our country.

All these subjects were derived from a single legend and it was not necessary to bring a story of suffering and subalternity, as is common in the presentation of black history. As John Henrik Clarke would say, “If you start your story in slavery, everything after that will feel like progress.” And we still have a lot to progress, so it’s important to bring the potential and fight in the history of this people.

With the partnership of area professors, it was possible to expand the conversations to different fields and thus explore different formats. Professor Vinícius greatly contributed to our journey, both in activities with the children and in the exchange of ideas, where I was able to learn about different narratives on multiple topics. In an exchange with the team, it is possible to enrich and think about possible ways to contemplate the countless archetypes of our society.

To encourage and contribute to the formation

of citizens who understand cultural plurality and deal positively with differences, it is necessary to deconstruct a curriculum that is still presented in a historically Eurocentric format. In the development of a decolonial work, it is important to recognize the existing political implications in the documents that are made available for the maintenance of territories of power, to then trace shortcuts to an education that frees us from historical ties. Antônio Flávio Moreira and Tomaz Tadeu da Silva say:

“ The curriculum is not an innocent and neutral element of disinterested transmission of social knowledge. The curriculum is implicated in power relations, the curriculum conveys particular and interesting social views, and the curriculum produces particular individual and social identities. The curriculum is not a transcendent and timeless element – it has a history, linked to specific and contingent forms of organization of society and education ”.

Knowing this, we started to fight for a change not only in the curriculum, but in the postures adopted in our daily lives and, mainly, in our practice. Literature is a great ally. In addition to encouraging the habit of reading, contributing to the development of creativity, and providing emotional, social, and cognitive development, it is possible to bring “common” stories, which do not necessarily deal with a militancy theme, but which have dark-skinned characters, something that is not customary in toys for children and this means that more and more black children find representation and identification and white children can also perceive black people in places of protagonism.

One of the first stories I took to the group was ‘Little Red Riding Hood and the Pink Boto, from a collection of re-signified classic tales by Mazza. This story takes place on the banks of the Negro River, in the Amazon, the girl lives with her mother in a village of floating houses and while taking a basket of tacacá and fruits from the region to her sick grandmother, she talks to a pink river dolphin and gets distracted by the beauties of the forest. The little red riding hood with black fur on the cover caught my attention right away. Some even questioned that that couldn’t be the story of Little Riding Hood because “Little Riding Hood is not like

that” - it was the speech of a child. We then started a conversation about what the story of Chapeuzinho was about and what would be essential for us to classify the story and recognize the character. Throughout the conversation, we were building the understanding that there are no physical characteristics that put characters in their places. Characters belong to imagination and possibilities. Each narrative is composed of an idealization and even though in our imagination and some descriptions, princesses, princes, and prominent characters appear as European stereotypes, there is not just one perspective, as we are made up of many peoples.

In every collection of Mazza’s resignified short stories, the characters are black and racial issues are not raised, but bring characteristics of our regionality, give Brazilianness to the narrative, bring our fauna, flora, and legends as an integral part of our culture and thus it was possible to address themes relevant and contributors in the perspective of breaking a Eurocentric narrative and disconnected from reality. In Rodriguez’s words:

“... reading is one of the ways children understand and interpret the world, bringing cultural and social enrichment, contributing to cognitive and psychological development, in addition to language appropriation.”

In addition to relying on the help of literature as a tool, we organically included black figures in our daily lives through the proposals in the handouts, the forms made in our routine and some, intentionally, went on weekends to be done with the families. Gradually, figures from different cultural backgrounds were introduced into our praxis and the group’s imagination, causing us to no longer have reactions of estrangement, but of awakening curiosity.

The group experienced contact with black culture in different ways. We know jokes, legends, cuisines, and geography. Even our project 'Mundo dos Dinossauros', from the second half of the year, traveled across the African continent, paralleling our folklore. During our research on Brazilian dinosaurs, we met a dinosaur called Sacisaurus. With this name and its bony characteristics, there was no way we could not return to legends and jokes.

With the book 'Kakokopi, Kakopi! Playing and playing with children from twenty African countries, we got to know many fun games from different regions and one of them became the most beloved in Pre 1, Sasakuru. The game consists of joining friends back to back and arm in arm and trying to reach the finish line balancing on one leg. Evaluating the characteristics of the group and taking into account issues of body maturation, we did not try to run with just one leg, but the challenge of arm-in-arm, back, and orderly walking was great fun. We play many times and the class often asks to play again. The video below illustrates one of these experiences:

CONCLUSION

This work aimed to share the daily anguish of teachers who seek to break with slavery currents by promoting an anti-racist education within a school environment, specifically with young children, where it becomes more sensitive and delicate to deal with issues like this.

Sharing the path traveled with the pre-1 class during this year of 2022 is a way of making available to my colleagues the possibilities thought of during that period, but with the attention of other committed teachers and a joint reflection can be transformed and improved. to remain in search of the annihilation of unfair and inhumane practices that affect the dignity of human beings.

I believe that the professionals who were formed after the enactment of Law 10.639/03, whether in the area of pedagogy or in any other course that has the option of doing a degree, should have in their curricula, if not full, enough foundation for them that they should promote in classrooms, after all, the law contemplates interdisciplinarity, it is not limited to history classes.

We walk at a slow pace, but little by little it is possible to witness changes. When a 5-year-old child, while making a self-portrait drawing, clarifies to his friends that there is no such thing as “skin color” because each skin has a tone and, therefore, there are different skin colors and a pencil color cannot be an only one representative, we noticed that the new generation develops more alert and attentive. It is in this direction that I want to go and will continue to provide myself with information to be able to supply whatever is of interest to these small citizens who are already interested in transforming their futures. I recall here a famous line by Angela Davis, an American philosopher activist: “It is not enough not to be racist, you must be anti-racist”.

I became a teacher because I believe in education as the greatest tool for transformation and although it is not an easy profession, it is perhaps the most rewarding in the world. We see the result of our work bloom daily, little by little until it becomes big and potent. I wish to be able to witness this group fill up with arguments and strength to contribute to a struggle that does not belong only to black people. Even though the majority of children in our school are fair-skinned people, we must work together so that we can count on white people as allies. Unfortunately, it is still necessary to think strategically about the paths outlined and my practice is always in motion, alert, and always contributing.

“If education alone does not transform society, without it society does not change either.” Paulo Freire

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POA ACTIONS IN SME-SP PUBLICATIONS IN THE YEARS 2018 AND 2019

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ABSTRACT

The educational public policy Professor Orientador de Área (POA) was instituted by Normative Instruction SME nº 25, of December 11, 2018, in Elementary School of the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo, to contribute to the implementation of the new Curriculum of the City of São Paulo and, based on this, monitoring the planning of actions by the professionals involved. The general objective of this research was to analyze whether the legal apparatus determined by the respective Municipal Department of Education favored the performance of the function. To this end, in a qualitative approach, a documentary and descriptive research was developed, which considered the context of reality and the variables relevant to the investigation, through a State of the Art and Content Analysis. In view of the analysis of the normative acts involved in the implementation of the POA public policy, it was verified that there was a legal guarantee in the dimension of the participation of the professional designated for the function in the training and his performance with the peers, in the collective schedules of teaching study to deepen didactic-pedagogical studies, improve practices and implement them in guaranteeing student learning. This public policy is undoubtedly innovative and relevant, although the size of RME-SP demands complex and specific logistics.

Keywords: education; educational public policy; curriculum; teacher training; area guidance professor.

INTRODUCTION

The educational public policy Professor Orientador de Área (POA) was instituted by Normative Instruction SME nº 25, of December 11, 2018, in Elementary School of the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo, to contribute to the implementation of the new Curriculum of the City of São Paulo and, based on this, in monitoring the planning of actions by the professionals involved. The POA constitutes the function destined to the effective teacher in the area of his attribution - Portuguese Language (Interdisciplinary and Authorial Cycles), Mathematics (Interdisciplinary and Authorial Cycles) or Teacher of Early Childhood Education and Elementary School I (PEIEF-I: Literacy Cycle) (SÃO PAULO, 2018b).

Considering this determination, the present research sought to identify whether the normative acts published by SME-SP, specifically regarding the POA public policy, favored the performance of the designated professor's function and, given the lack of definition of the profiles to characterize this recent task, it was decided to carry out a survey of the context in which it was cited in the digital public archives of the SME-SP during the period 2018 and 2019. That is, a parallel was built between the ideal identified in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME nº 25/2018, as well as in institutional guidance publications, and under the conditions determined in subsequent normative acts. In this perspective, Content Analysis techniques (BARDIN, 2016) were used, aiming to understand the manifest and latent discourse identified, as a result of verifying the presence, absence and frequency of the registration units that make up the categories coded from the scanned documents.

DEVELOPMENT

The research began by identifying registration units in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME No. 25/2018, which address the function, objectives and specific attributions of the POA. Having carried out the State of the Art of the theme through documentary research in strictly written and primary, contemporary and retrospective sources (LAKATOS; MARCONI, 2018a), data collection techniques were applied, which enabled

the elaboration of the mental map (Figure 1) which provided the first foundations for the creation of the research project.

Figure 1 – Pre-analysis : Mind map

Source: Prepared by the author (2019).

A first hypothesis (that the POA would allow the improvement of teachers' actions, from a perspective of integral, inclusive and equitable education) required an initial immersion in IN SME nº 25/2018 to identify the registration units and possible categories of analysis aligned with the objectives and attributions of the role, along with excerpts from this document. After further reading this Instruction, as well as gathering the other materials that make up the corpus, it was verified the need to focus on the registration units identified in Articles 3, 4 and 17, grouped into categories relevant to the research.

Finally, to distinguish the specific actions of the POA (mentioned in the publications of the SME-SP) we returned to the treatment of the material gathered with the Study of Art engaged in digital public archives, namely: portals of the Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo, the São Paulo City Department of Education, the Union of Education Specialists in Public Education in São Paulo and the Open Data Portals and Municipal Legislation.

The material was prepared in a word processor for better viewing and detection of terms through the Navigation Panel, highlighting the header and closing of each normative act, eliminating unnecessary numbering markers and adapting the font color.

After being saved in a word processor and having

detected (via the Navigation Panel) the pertinent citations, the 44 (forty-four) files – each arranged in tables containing a description and clipping – were grouped in folders, firstly according to the year of publication (2018 and 2019) and the discursive genre institutional guidelines and normative acts. The latter, given the diversity of purposes, were later grouped into POA-specific communications, non-POA-specific communications, registration opening communications, homologation dispatch, ordinances and normative instructions published in 2018 and 2019.

In this research, the variables are the categories constituted by the aspects that best characterize the POA public policy, using significant topics as a selection criterion for these aspects, that is, registration units present in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME n° 25/2018, which address the role, objectives and specific attributions of the POA.

In that section, the registration units were selected and, after studying and analyzing these terms in the other documents that make up the research corpus, there was a need to group them into 3 (three) categories, as shown in Chart 1, according to criterion of the topics that cover the respective registration units in the referred Articles: public policy, objectives and specific attributions.

Table 1 - Registration units and categories for analysis

Registration Units	Categories
Area Guiding Professor - POA (act) together with the Pedagogical Coordinator	Public policy
Implementation of the Curriculum of the City of São Paulo	
collaborate in the implementation of the Educational Policy	
contribute to the improvement of IDEB indexes	Goals
favor the development of a Political-Pedagogical Project	
(auxiliary) integration of the different Knowledge Areas	
constantly improve actions, based on the City's Curriculum	
participate in the planning of the didactic action together with the teachers	Specific Assignments
prepare annual work plan	
record [...] the pedagogical documentation accompanying the teaching planning	
Identify inconsistencies in the development of teaching and learning processes and propose interventions	

Source: Prepared by the author (2021)

Subsequently, the search for the terms POA and Professor Orientador de Área (both simultaneously) in the Google Scholar database and in public digital archives – portals of the Official Gazette of the

City of São Paulo, the Municipal Department of Education, the Union of Specialists in São Paulo Municipal Public School Education (SINESP) and the Open Data and Municipal Legislation Portals – showed that the research was unprecedented and there was a sufficient number of documents to carry out the State of the Art on the subject.

The use of the word processor, as well as its Navigation Panel, enabled the data collection process aimed at selecting and counting the recording units and their categories, making it possible to detect the presence, absence and frequency of variables in the documents. The charts were built with this same tool, but the figures and schemes were created in the program for creating/editing and displaying graphic presentations. During this process, notes and comments on the selected data were attached to the documents and the analysis of the selected information (especially in relation to Sobral's experience) required the search for other documents and data collection on the portals of DIEESE, OXFAM, IDEB, QEdU and IBEGE.

The spreadsheet editor was used to organize the data and process the information, with a view to discussing and analyzing the results and preparing the report.

Successive normative acts guided the actions of the implementation of this public policy, investing it with intentionality, attributions and specific training – represented in the summary presented in the Tables below.

At the end of 2018, there were the initial normative acts for the implementation of the POA, which make up Group 1 of analysis, present in Table 2.

Table 2 - Group 1: Normative Acts published in DO.online - Year 2018

Normative Acts published in DO.online - Year 2018	Categories
IN SME n° 22, 12/11/2018: Provides for the organization of early childhood education units, elementary education, elementary and secondary education and unified educational centers of the municipal education network for the year 2019, and other measures.	Public policy
IN SME No. 25, 12/11/2018: Provides for the organization of the complementary pedagogical support project - recovery, as well as the appointment of teachers to exercise the functions of pedagogical support	Public policy Goals

teacher - PAP and Area Advisor Professor - POA and make other arrangements	Assignments
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Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

At specific moments of the semesters, SME-SP published guiding institutional documents, in which the role of the POA was mentioned, as shown in Table 3, constituting Group 2 for analysis.

Table 3 – Group 2: Institutional Guidance Publications

Institutional Guidance Publications available on the SME-SP Portal	Categories
THE CURRICULUM OF THE CITY OF SÃO PAULO: An experience of updating and implementing curriculum for Elementary School based on the BNCC	Public policy Assignments
School Organization Meeting 2019 DRES / UEs	Public policy
Guidelines for Educational Units: 2nd semester - 2019	Public policy Assignments
Guiding document for the Portuguese language survey: Literacy Cycle - Elementary School	Assignments

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Analysis Group 3 is composed of the successive normative acts published during the year 2019. Due to its quantity and diversity of purposes, it was subdivided into 5 (five) groupings.

Table 4 lists the call notices to fill the POA vacancy in the mentioned EU.

Table 4 – GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Registration open

Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2019: registration opening	Categories
COMMUNICATE NO. 35 OF APRIL 4, 2019 04/06/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 52 DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy
COMMUNICATE No. 20, 04/22/2019 04/26/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 93 DIRECTOR OF GUAIANASES	Public policy
COMMUNICATION No. 72 of 11/26/2019 11/28/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 48 DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy
COMMUNICATION No. 42 OF 12/05/2019 12/07/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 34 DRE PIRITUBA/JARAGUÁ	Public policy
COMMUNICATE NO. 73 OF DECEMBER 2019 12/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 56 DRE SÃO MIGUEL	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Table 5 contains the announcements of continuing teacher training courses specific to the POA, to be taught by the SME-SP team of trainers.

Table 5 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Specific announcements to POA

Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Specific notices to POA	Categories
COMMUNICATE No. 243, OF 03/27/2019. Making the publication in the DO.online of 04/09/2019, page 42	Public policy Goals
03/28/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 36 COMMUNICATE No. 243 OF MARCH 27, 2019. Promoter area: SME/COPED/DIEFEM Made void with publication No. 313, of April 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
04/18/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 41 COMMUNICATE No. 313, OF APRIL 17, 2019. Promoter area: DIEFEM Making the publication in the DO.online of 03/28/2019, PAGE. 36 Rectified by the publication of the DO.online of 04/18/2019 - page 41 COMMUNICATE NO. 313 OF APRIL 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/27/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 37 Education. Secretary's Office Rectification of the DO.online publication of 04/18/2019 – page 41 COMMUNICATE No. 313, OF APRIL 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
04/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 42 COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019. Promoter area: SME / COPED / DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
04/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 42 COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019. Promoter area: SME / COPED / DIEFEM Corrected by the publication of communiqué n° 295, of April 11, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/16/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 37 Rectification of the DO.online publication of 04/12/2019 – page 42. COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019.	Public policy Goals
Rectification of publication of DO.online of 08/14/2019 - page 42 COMMUNICATION No. 608, OF AUGUST 13, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 33 COMMUNICATION No. 624, OF AUGUST 19, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
08/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 42 Education. Secretary's Office COMMUNICATE No. 608 OF AUGUST 13, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM Corrected by the publication of communiqué n° 608, of August 13, 2019.	Public policy Goals

(to be continued)
(conclusion)

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Table 6 contains the announcements of continuing teacher training courses that are not exclusive to teachers assigned to the role of POA, but specific to this public policy.

Table 6 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Announcements not specific to POA

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Announcements not specific to POA	Categories
07/30/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 37 COMMUNICATION No. 554 OF JULY 29, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
05/15/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 47 COMMUNICATE No. 385 OF MAY 14, 2019 Promoter area: ELEMENTARY AND HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATION DIVISION	Public policy Goals
07/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 48 COMMUNICATION No. 507, OF JULY 11, 2019. Promoter areas: COPED/DIEFEM/UNICEU	Public policy Goals
07/17/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 32 COMMUNICATE No. 39, OF APRIL 12, 2019. Promoter area: DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy Goals
07/26/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 34 COMMUNICATE No. 36, JULY 23, 2019. Promoter area: DRE/DIPED ITAQUERA	Public policy Goals
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 34 COMMUNICATE No. 36, OF AUGUST 14, 2019 Promoter area: DIPED IPIRANGA .	Public policy Goals
08/28/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 33 COMMUNICATION No. 648, OF AUGUST 27, 2019 Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM .	Public policy Goals
11/19/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 47 COMMUNICATE No. 823, OF NOVEMBER 18, 2019. Promoter area: DIEFEM	Public policy Goals

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

In Table 7, there is the approval of the course prepared by Sindsep , aimed at professionals affiliated to this union, including those designated as POA, therefore, not specific to this.

Table 7 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Approval order

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Approval order	Categories
08/29/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 47 Education. Secretary's Office Approval Order No. 19378 COURSE: Considerations on the Curriculum of the City: Early Childhood Education	Goals

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

The ordinances, listed in Table 8, deal with the authorization of the waiver of a point at the time coinciding with the event, safeguarding the time for locomotion, for teachers who participate in training courses specific to the work of the POA, that is, the time of moving around and staying on the course was considered a day worked.

Table 8 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Ordinances

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019: Ordinances	Categories
04/18/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 19 ORDINANCE No. 3.791, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
ORDINANCE No. 3.792, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
ORDINANCE No. 3.793, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
07/30/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 16 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 5.950, OF JULY 29, 2019	Public policy
08/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 19 ORDINANCE No. 6,364, OF AUGUST 13, 2019	Public policy
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 14 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 6.553, OF AUGUST 19, 2019	Public policy
08/24/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 17 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 6.686, OF AUGUST 22, 2019	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Chart 9 is composed of Analysis Group 4, where the Normative Instructions published in 2019 are gathered, with a view to improving the implementation of the POA public policy.

Table 9 - GROUP 4: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019

GROUP 4: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019	Categories
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 14, OF JUNE 5, 2019 Amends Normative Instruction No. 25, of 12/11/18, provides for the organization of the Complementary Pedagogical Support Project - Recovery, as well as for the appointment of teachers to exercise the functions of Pedagogical Support Professor - PAP and Area Guiding Professor - POA and other provisions.	Public policy Goals
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 31 OF OCTOBER 31, 2019 Deals with the reorganization of the function of the Area Guiding Professor - POA, and other measures.	Public policy Goals Assignments
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 40, 11/29/2019 Deals with the Initial Process of Choosing/Assigning Shifts and Classes/Blocks/Classes to Teachers of the Municipal Education Network - RME, who work in Municipal Child Education Centers - CEMEIs, Municipal Infant Education Schools - EMEIs , Municipal Schools of Elementary Education - EMEFs, Municipal Elementary and Secondary Education Schools, Municipal Bilingual Education Schools for the Deaf - EMEBSs, Municipal Elementary and Secondary Education Schools - EMEFMs and Integrated Youth and Adult Education Centers - CIEJAs and other measures.	Public policy
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 45, OF DECEMBER 11, 2019 Provides for the organization of early childhood education units, elementary education, primary and secondary education and unified educational centers of the municipal education network for the year 2020, and makes other provisions.	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

CONCLUSION

It was found that in the various documents directed to the POA, the function is continually mentioned associated with its specificity in contributing to the implementation of the Curriculum of the City of São Paulo, giving credibility to its actions. Emphasis is identified on the delimitation of certain times for the deepening of studies and reflection on practices, essentially with their peers, an essential routine. Acting as a teaching partner of CP, the POA has access to differentiated training that accredits him/her to encourage the teaching team to:

- Strengthen the implementation of the City Curriculum;
- Understand the concept of literacy present in the City's Curriculum;
- Reflect on the didactic work as an object of knowledge and on the text as an object of teaching;
- Reflect on pedagogical strategies;
- Identify organizational modalities in a pedagogical routine;
- Analyze didactic situations and sequences of activities and case studies.
- Reflect on the different ways of organizing the room to encourage exchange and construction of knowledge;
- Share experiences;
- Analyze students' productions, with a view to teacher interaction and intervention;
- Adapt and take advantage of available resources;
- Participate in the territory's educational community.

However, the performance of the POA has as a parameter its continuous alignment with the CP, when studying the theoretical and methodological assumptions of the City's Curriculum in order to subsidize the work of the POA; reflect on strategies for monitoring learning and relating them to the importance of the teaching lesson plan, as well as the characteristics that need to be present in teaching practices in the classroom; promote Professional Reading to deepen knowledge and Professional Writing to problematize the difficulties experienced; and to critically analyze POA practices to support the planning of didactic action together

with the professors of the component that it holds and with the CP.

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POST-STROKE DEPRESSION: NEUROCOGNITIVE EVALUATION AND REHABILITATION

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ABSTRACT

Cerebral Vascular Accident (CVA) is a neurological condition considered one of the greatest concerns in public health, due to the significant burden of disability and dependence. In this article, a theoretical review is carried out focused on the signs and symptoms presented in patients in an ischemic process, considering that studies reveal that among the symptoms, post-stroke depression (PAVC) is the most frequent emotional disorder. CVPD has a high prevalence, and despite this, it is poorly detected and treated. Many risk factors and negative repercussions on patient recovery are associated with CVAPD. Thus, knowing the nature and its risk factors becomes essential to improve its diagnosis and treatment, since its study is considered relevant due to the important contribution of neuropsychology in the course of brain disorders, specifically cognitive changes associated with Cerebral Vascular accidents (CVA).) and the relationship between the neuropsychological findings and the presence of depression in these patients, allowing a broader analysis of the need for studies that take into account the relationships between mood and functioning cognitive.

Keywords: Stroke; Depression; Cognitive Assessment; Neuropsychological rehabilitation.

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral Vascular Accident (CVA) is defined as a vascular aggression that causes a lesion in the brain, resulting in neurological deficits. However, the term evolves to include injuries caused by hemodynamic and coagulation disorders, even in the absence of detectable changes in arteries and veins, thus vascular injury must be understood in a broader context of the complex interactions between the vessel (endothelium), figurative elements of the blood and hemodynamic variables (ANDRÉ, 2006).

Stroke is a chronic neurological condition classified as one of the most prevalent diseases worldwide, with 15 million victims each year. Considered one of the most important causes of disability in developed and underdeveloped countries. Being the leading cause of disability in adults in the United States and Canada. Although stroke death rates in North America have shown substantial declines, approximately millions of Americans and 300,000 Canadians are currently living with the effects of stroke. Differences in stroke severity and symptoms depend on the affected brain region.

The literature describes that cerebrovascular diseases (CVD) are the third cause of death in the world, second only to heart diseases in general and cancer. Around 40 to 50% of individuals who suffer a stroke die during the first months that follow (ANDRÉ, 2006). According to Fukujima (2005), in Brazil, stroke is considered among the most cause of death in adults, and is also one of the most disabling diseases, with high rates of mortality, disability, and high social and economic cost.

Depression is the most frequent psychiatric complication of stroke. Post-stroke depression (PAVC), that is, that which occurs after the stroke, is associated with increased mortality, greater impairment in physical and language functioning, longer hospitalization, and reduced quality of life. Studies reveal that depression has been little considered in stroke patients, so much so that its diagnosis is made in 20% to 50% of cases. The etiology of CVAPD is multifactorial. Despite these data, the occurrence of CAPD has been associated with some risk factors, such as female gender, younger age, precarious social network, history of depressive disorder and

history of previous strokes, psychological factors resulting from damage caused by neurological sequelae, hormonal factors such as changes in the pituitary-hypothalamus-adrenal axis (HHA), neuropsychological deficits, and location of the stroke. When CVAPD is diagnosed and treated, there is an improvement in functional recovery and a reduction in cognitive impairment (TERRONI et al., 2009).

According to Paula (et al., 2008), more and more scientific studies developed to investigate the Central Nervous System (CNS) are considering, in addition to their neuroanatomical substrates, the cognitive and behavioral aspects dealt with by neuropsychology. In the specific case of stroke, cognitive and affective changes are frequent, both in the acute phase and in the rehabilitation period, making its investigation fundamental.

In clinical practice, neuropsychological techniques have contributed significantly to the treatment of the disease. Performs comparative and qualitative analysis of the results obtained, allowing a relationship between the patient's history, behavior, and neurological dysfunction; the correlation with the information coming from other exams and the patient's clinical condition. However, from a scientific point of view, it is still not known with clarity which cognitive functions are involved, which neuropsychological instruments are most indicated, which are the relationships between cognition and depression, or even between cognition and injury resulting from stroke (PAULA et al. , 2008).

Neuropsychology studies cognitive, emotional, and personality disorders caused by brain damage. It is also called behavioral neurology because the brain expresses the injuries suffered in behavioral disorders. It has diagnostic, therapeutic, and cognitive objectives, enabling the raising of hypotheses about normal brain functioning (GIL, 2002).

Therefore, the neurocognitive assessment of patients after brain injury is important to complement the classic studies of aphasia with tests based on cognitive models of language. In turn, neuropsychological rehabilitation is necessary, given that Neuropsychology provides techniques that make it possible to treat the appropriate

changes (TOAZZA, 2010).

REVISION OF LITERATURE

Cerebral Vascular accidents (CVA) can cause cognitive and emotional damage to memory and language, visuospatial functions, executive functions, attention, and even mood swings. Regarding emotional aspects, depression seems to be the most prevalent disorder, depending on the location and laterality of the lesion, and the most evident behavioral changes occur in compulsive behavior, lack of inhibitory control, and obsessive-compulsive behavior (TERRONI, et al., 2003).

The first to note that people with the cerebrovascular disease were vulnerable to depression was Kraepelin (1901/1915), in which depression would be an understandable reaction to brain injury. A study published in the *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* in 2009 reveals that the prevalence of post-stroke depression ranges from 23% to 60%. In addition, it suggests the fact that CVAPD is associated with worse prognosis and evolution, worsening of cognitive dysfunctions, and reduced quality of life, with stroke affecting the basal ganglia, left frontal region, and/or structures of the prefrontosubcortical circuit, and, it is related to the frequency and severity of CVAPD, that is, the study found that patients with depression had more frequent infarctions, affecting the prefrontosubcortical circuit or some of its structures: caudate, pallidum, genu of the internal capsule and anterior capsule, especially in the left hemisphere (TERRONI et al., 2009).

Another study, also published in the *Revista de Psiquiatria Clínica*, in 2010, reveals that post-stroke depression is an underdiagnosed condition since only about 30% of patients with this condition are diagnosed by physicians who are not psychiatrists. Several studies have demonstrated the therapeutic efficacy of antidepressants such as nortriptyline, fluoxetine, and citalopram in the treatment of post-stroke depression. However, the biggest current obstacle is not the treatment of this pathology, but its diagnosis (SOUZA et al., 2010).

In a case study, Reichelt & Fraga (2006) sought subsidies to substantiate the occurrence of post-stroke depression and its consequences in an

individual's life. It was observed that the results of the neuropsychological assessment pointed to depression, from the conduct of observations and interviews to the neuropsychological tests and tests. The losses found in the tests in the areas of memory and attention, which depend on the state of humor, added to the aspects of the conduct depression, informed by the family and by the patient, suggested a post-stroke depression, depicting in a framework on which a syndrome resulting from the interaction between functional and neurological factors is configured, where humor played a fundamental role, both in terms of what preceded ischemia as in the post-ischemia phase. In short, acting as cause and consequence (REICHELT & FRAGA, 2006).

Depression severity is also associated with functional and cognitive impairment in all domains. Generally, depending on the size of the lesion, the neuropsychological profile of patients with moderate and severe depressive symptoms may be affected, causing damage to memory, visual perception, and language domains (TERRONI et al., 2009).

The neuropsychocognitive assessment of post-brain injury patients is important to complete the classic studies of aphasias with tests based on cognitive models of language. Their results address not only the cognitive deficits caused by the neurological injury but also the skills preserved and possible strategies for rehabilitation. Not only do they help to better characterize the condition, but they also raise fundamental information for the therapeutic planning of cognitive rehabilitation. Despite the diffusion of international neurocognitive assessment instruments, Brazilian tests are still rare, justifying the importance of finding out how they are being performed nationally in post-stroke patients (TOAZZA, 2010).

The use of a neuropsychological battery enables a better analysis of the cognitive impairments in these patients (TERRONI, 2009). Impairments in cognition may be related to poor quality of life in the long term in ischemic strokes, among which, affect functions, the author Scheffer et al. (2013) points out:

[...] neuropsychological rehabilitation is necessary, considering that Neuropsychology provides techniques

that make it possible to treat the necessary alterations, which are extremely important and establishes which among the available tools are the most appropriate for the objective to be achieved in the context of cognitive and emotional rehabilitation (SCHEFFER et al., 2013 apud NOREÑA, 2010).

Cognitive rehabilitation is considered one of the components of neuropsychological rehabilitation. According to Fuentes (2008, p.399) cognitive rehabilitation “is a clinical area of interdisciplinary action that seeks both recovery and compensation for altered cognitive functions resulting from brain damage”. Among its functions, the rehabilitation neuropsychology encompasses a combination of psychotherapy, family participation through groups, and therapeutic instructions to patients, always being carried out within a multidisciplinary context.

For patients affected by stroke, the objectives of rehabilitation are: to prevent complications; recover as much of the brain functions compromised by the stroke as possible, which may be temporary or permanent; return the patient to social life, both in the family and at work, reintegrating him with the best possible quality of life (SCHEFFER et al., 2013 apud Damiani & Yokoo, 2002).

To Silva (2010, p.24) “Cognitive rehabilitation concentrates efforts to help patients understand their limitations and compensate or restore lost functions to improve adaptation and facilitate independence”. The Neuropsychologist will carry out an assessment to identify deficits and cognitive abilities, considering it within the individual’s personal and social context. This intervention may also involve caregiver education and support (SILVA, 2010).

In general, it can be said that the main objective of rehabilitation is the optimization of physical, vocational, and social functioning after an illness or neurological damage. Munõz and Ruiz (1999) propose as basic objectives of a neuropsychological rehabilitation program; 1) provide a model that helps the patient and his family to understand

what happened; 2) provide skills training strategies to recover and compensate for cognitive deficits, improve the patient’s performance in different social situations and help him to establish realistic work commitments and interpersonal relationships; 3) promote a realistic environment of hope. (CANCELA, 2008 apud Munõz and Ruiz, 1999).

Patients’ recovery targets the affected areas and recovery should start as soon as possible. In addition to the motor and cognitive consequences, which are direct consequences of the injury, there are psychological changes at an emotional level (anxiety and depression), discouragement, as well as self-reference variables, such as self-efficacy, self-concept, self-esteem, and social support, which will affect the patient’s commitment to recovery. The decrease in expectations due to the interaction of cognitive, and emotional variables is physical, reduces the patient’s motivation to commit to recovery, being more serious the more advanced the patient’s age is (PAIS RIBEIRO, 2005).

In the field of care, the literature reports on the low level of detection of CVADD and, consequently, a large number of patients who do not receive adequate treatment. Bearing in mind that the treatment is efficient, leading to remission of CVAPD and, in turn, improving the evolution and prognosis of patients regarding the recovery of losses resulting from the stroke. In terms of the high rate of depression, it suggests the need for monitoring and evaluation of programs that include interventions to treat depressive symptoms and AVCAD. The repercussions of stroke on individuals are many, and knowledge of factors associated with quality of life after stroke can provide valuable information on strategies that can be used by health professionals to improve outcomes in the treatment of patients with CVAPD (TERRONI, 2009).

The aforementioned author warns that in the sphere of scientific investigation, in general, there is great variation in methodology in the various areas of study of DPAVC. The possibility of replicating the studies is necessary to verify the evidence. The inclusion in studies of patients with depression before stroke brings characteristics and risk factors that interfere with the analysis of results. For example, instead of studying post-stroke depression, we would be studying recurrent depression

triggered by a stroke. Therefore, this is crucial for the analysis of the neuroanatomical correlates of CVAPD. Longitudinal studies are needed and may clarify the nature of the association between CVPD and neurocognitive changes (Ibid.).

CONCLUSIONS

The relationships between depression and stroke appear to be bidirectional and influenced by both emotional and neurological conditions. Although studies have not yet been able to clearly explain such relationships, research aimed at clarifying the pathophysiology of post-stroke depression remains in development and could bring valuable contributions to the treatment of these patients and the improvement of their quality of life (PAULA et al., 2008).

The author also reveals that studies of the neuropsychological aspects of this disease are of great importance, allowing various aspects studied in these patients, such as their personality and history, to come to identify possible risk factors for depression. And, it also, allows a better understanding of the critical state of post-stroke depression, paving the way for the search for more effective theories of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of possible cognitive sequelae in patients. Thus, neuropsychology, in turn, has been improving in the development of techniques capable of identifying such dysfunctions and specific neuropsychological patterns in post-stroke depression (Ibidem).

According to Terroni (2003), a method that can also contribute to greater knowledge about the pathophysiology of post-stroke depression in future research is the investigation of neuroanatomical areas affected by the stroke as risk factors for post-stroke depression (TERRONI, et al. ., 2003).

Toazza (2010) warns of the reduced number of standardized and available Brazilian neuropsychological instruments, considering the few instruments validated in the country or produced for the Brazilian population. There is an urgent need for further research in this area to provide a more adequate survey of cognitive symptoms in the clinical population, especially post-stroke, precisely because it is the most frequent

cause of language disorders.

Therefore, the literature describes that CAPD is very frequent and underdiagnosed. Several risk factors are involved in the occurrence of CVAPD. The negative repercussions of depression in stroke patients are many and significant, as studies have pointed out. Improved knowledge about the factors involved in CVAPD can help improve efficient therapeutic intervention and increase diagnostic accuracy (TERRONI et al., 2009).

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